

TOPONYMS USED IN THE LANGUAGE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract

The study of the structure of language and the lexical layer used in different historical periods. In particular, the emergence of new conceptual understanding in the language during the years of national revival. The research and study of toponyms in the language of textbooks by linguistic scholars proves that the frequency of the use of toponyms in textbooks has increased compared to other linguistic units.

Keywords: lexical layer, textbooks, toponyms, national spirit, types of toponyms.

Just as written sources play a great and irreplaceable role in studying the history of a nation, a country, and a language, toponyms are equally significant. In resolving controversial issues related to the history and ethnogenesis of a nation and its language, toponyms, which occupy a special place among onomastic units, have a high position. Toponyms, along with being a valuable treasure that reflects the geographical situation of the territory inhabited by the people, also serve as a source informing us about the migration, assimilation, occupations, and crafts of tribes, clans, and nations. T. Bakhshiyeva writes: "...based on them, we can trace the processes and changes that occurred from time to time, step by step, in the toponymic system and geographical names. Sources provide valuable facts for the scientific explanation of toponymic units". Toponyms are the names of cities and villages, mountains and glaciers, rivers and lakes, bays and seas, forests and gardens, in short, all geographical objects. The study of these geographical object names from a linguistic perspective has always been relevant for our history. Toponyms are very interesting linguistic units because they are studied at the intersection of three sciences: history, geography, and linguistics. Historians, geographers, and linguists have all contributed to the study of toponyms. However, in our opinion, the greatest responsibility lies with linguists. "To study the history of a nation, its formation and development, and to identify ancient linguistic features, toponyms as well as paleotoponyms provide very rich material. It is impossible to imagine Azerbaijan or any other country in the world without toponyms." Y. B. Yusifov notes that "toponymic names are an important auxiliary historical source that helps in solving the problem of the formation of the Azerbaijani people" [132, p.70]. The role of toponyms in identifying the linguistic features of the population living in a certain territory is invaluable. Researchers have concluded that a name, like all words, is subject not to physical geography or political history but to the laws of language. Toponyms, like other lexical units, are based on models existing in the language. Toponyms are mainly formed from common lexical units. These mostly include the names of artificially created settlements rather than natural geographical objects.

In the Azerbaijani language, toponyms are classified as simple, derivative, and compound. In Azerbaijani toponymy, there are also compound toponyms that do not belong to attributive word combinations but

demonstrate certain syntactic relations between components. Among them are toponyms whose first component is in the accusative case. According to the type of geographical object indicated, toponyms are divided as follows:

1. Oikononyms – names of settlements. "Oikononyms are a type of toponyms that denote the names of settlements (villages, towns, cities) belonging to a certain territory. For example, when Mubariz was still a child, the Armenians first occupied Khojaly, then the fortress of Shusha, Kalbajar, Lachin, Aghdam, Fuzuli, Jabrayil, Gubadli, and Zangilan (M. Chamanli 'Hero Mubariz', p. 85). Or: 'We paid no heed / Neither to the blizzard nor the storm / We got into the cars / And set off for Nabran' (R. R. Yusifoglu, p.11). According to the Russian linguist A. V. Superinskaya, "toponyms are the mirror of history" [122, p.13]. Our historical place names live on in toponyms.

2. Urbanonyms – names of avenues, streets, squares, markets, fortresses, buildings, etc. For example, 'Friends lived in one of the tall buildings on Azadliq Avenue' (G. Ibrahimova, p. 35).

3. Choronyms – names of regions, provinces, republics, and countries that have a certain administrative-territorial division. For example: 'There is a mausoleum in Nakhchivan, built by Ajami' (Imanova S. "Momine Khatun Mausoleum", p.29).

4. Oronyms – names of places that differ from each other in the surface relief of the land. A large part of the toponymic layer in Azerbaijani onomastics consists of oronyms, which are actively used in children's literature during the years of independence. Examples: 'That is Mount Murov seen from afar, and this nearby one is Shahbulag' (M. Chamanli, 'Qurban Bayram', p.211); 'Balli Rock... Erimgeldi... Khachinderbend... Jidir Plain...' 'The underground is a treasure, the sky is my pure mirror' (Kh. R. Uluturk, p.176); 'You are the adornment of the Khizi forests, Qashqa Mountain' (R. Yusifoglu, p.20); 'Where are you coming from? – From the foothills of Shahdag' (R. Yusifoglu, p.33); 'You will go to Wolf Mountain' (G. Ibrahimova, 'A Sip of Water', p.125).

5. Dromonyms – names of air, water, overland, and underground transportation routes.

6. Hydronyms – names of rivers, lakes, canals, and seas. For example: 'At Cape Afon, throw them into the deep waters of the sea' (G. Ibrahimova, 'The Magic Doctor').

Oikonyms, denoting settlements belonging to a certain territory, are one of the most widespread types of toponyms in Azerbaijani toponymy. More than 4,500 toponyms consist of oikonyms. Depending on the scale of the area they designate, oikonyms are divided into comonyms and astionyms. A comonym refers to the name of a village settlement, while an astionym refers to the name of a city settlement. "Toponymy is organically connected with ethnonymy and anthroponymy. Many natural objects are named based on external appearance, economic features, or the names of their owners. As for the names of settlements, they are mainly formed either from nearby natural objects or from the names of tribes, clans, families, personal names, nicknames, etc." Since toponyms are subject to the laws and norms of the language, their role in identifying the linguistic features of a certain territory is invaluable. Like other lexical units, toponyms are based on models existing in the language. There are also cases where no common word is used in the toponym, which mainly applies to artificially created settlements. T. Ahmadov writes: "According to the principle of economy in language, the second components of toponyms—words indicating the type or kind of geographical object—often undergo ellipsis. As a result, the first components of various structures, which play a leading role in reflecting the specific features of the settlement name and form its core, are stabilized as oikonyms" [23, p.60]. The toponyms used in children's literature of the independence years are also diverse in origin. Foreign toponyms are often found in children's literature. For example: 'This is a photo of my grandfather, officer Mirza of the Tsar's army, taken in St. Petersburg' (A. Samadova, 'Ali and Zumurud's Magic Carpet', p.19); 'Two years ago, his only son moved with his family to Cologne, Germany' (R. Yusifgizi, 'The Green-Eyed Girl', p.14); 'The professor comes to America to work with an artificial intelligence society' (R. Yusifgizi, 'I Will Never Forget You', p.27). Sometimes utopian toponyms are also used in the children's literature of the

independence period. Such toponyms are purely products of the writer's imagination. For example: 'We are in the Corridor of Time, and this is the most beautiful miracle you have ever seen in your life' (A. Samadova, 'Ali and Zumurud's Magic Carpet', p.31); 'You will receive your primary education in the Land of Liars' (G. Ibrahimova, 'The Adventures of Sirius and Virus', p.47); 'In the Land of Microbes, microbes and viruses live and bacteria multiply' (G. Ibrahimova, 'The Adventures of Sirius and Virus', p.54); 'We are very glad that Sirius Mammadli has come to visit the Land of the Wise' (G. Ibrahimova, 'Journey to the Land of the Wise', p.27). A. Gurbanov, when discussing anthroponyms, mentions fictitious names. However, the scholar does not refer to fictitious toponyms or place names used in literature [50, p.168]. Yet, when we examine children's literature, we witness that such fictitious toponyms are also created by writers and poets as artistic devices and are used in their works.

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